

Three-dimensional MHD Casson Nanofluid Flow Past a Non-linearly Stretching Surface in Presence of Porous Media

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Abstract	The aim of this study is to analyse the three-dimensional magnetohydrodynamic Casson nanofluid flow past a non-linearly stretching surface in presence of porous media, radiation and heat source. Brownian motion and thermophoresis effects are considered. Similarity transformations are employed to convert the governing equations into ordinary differential equations. We use the BVP4C solver to compute the solution. A detailed discussion is provided based on the graphical and tabular representation of the impact of various parameters. Also Skin friction coefficient, Nusselt number and Sherwood number has been analyzed and presented in tabular form.
Keywords	MHD, Casson, Nanofluid, Flow, Non-linearly, Surface, Porous Media.
Introduction	In fluids mechanics, fluids are typically described as Newtonian or non-Newtonian, depending on how they respond to applied stress. Many researchers prioritize the study of non-Newtonian fluids over Newtonian fluids due to their extensive applications across industrial, technological, and scientific fields. In particular, non-Newtonian fluids play a significant role in biological systems, appearing in substances such as emulsions, sugar solutions, mud, chyme, apple sauce, blood at low shear rates, and various soaps. Among non-Newtonian fluids, Casson fluids are notable for their significant use in various industrial processes.
Objective of study	This work investigates the three-dimensional MHD Casson nanofluid flow over a nonlinearly stretching surface embedded in a porous medium. Using similarity transformations, the governing nonlinear partial differential equations for flow, heat, and mass transfer are converted into ordinary differential equations. These equations are solved numerically through the MATLAB <code>bvp4c</code> solver. The effects of different dimensionless parameters on velocity, temperature, and concentration profiles are discussed and shown in graphical form (1-11). Additionally, the skin friction coefficient, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number are computed and summarized in tables.
Review of Literature	Khan and pop [1] studied the boundary layer analysis of nanofluid flow past a stretching sheet. Haq RU et al. [2] have elaborated the Magnetohydrodynamic Stagnation point flow of nanofluid over a stretching sheet with consideration of slip and thermal radiation effects. Mustafa M and Khan JA [3] have studied the analysis of Casson nanofluid flow over a non-linearly stretching sheet in the presence of Magnetic effects. Mahanta G and Shaw S [4] have analysed the three-dimensional Casson fluid flow over a porous linearly stretching sheet with convective boundary condition. Analysis of 3D induced nanofluid flow over an exponentially stretching sheet was studied by J. A. Khan et al. [5]. G. T. Thammanna et al. [6] have discussed the Unsteady three-dimensional MHD flow of a Casson fluid past a stretching surface in the presence of chemical reaction. Prathi V. Kumar et al. [7] have analysed the study of three dimensional radiative magnetohydrodynamic Casson nanofluid over an exponential porous stretching sheet with heat source under convective boundary conditions. Three-dimensional magnetohydrodynamic mixed convection flow of a Casson nanofluid considering Hall and ion slip effects were investigated by Wubshet and Temesgen [8]. Usha alaria and Anil Sharma [9] have investigated the free convective MHD flow of Casson fluid in porous media bounded by Semi-Infinite non-isothermal stretching sheet with heat and mass transfer. Jima Seyoum Abert et al. [10] investigated the three-dimensional Magnetohydrodynamics Casson fluid flow past a non-linearly stretching surface with nanoparticles. Usha alaria and Anil Sharma [11] have studied the three-dimensional MHD stagnation-point flow of Maxwell fluid over a stretching sheet with Soret and Dufour effects.
Main Text	Mathematical formulation

A 3D steady incompressible Casson nanofluid flow over a non-linear stretching surface is considered under the combined effects of porous media, thermal radiation, heat generation, and magnetohydrodynamics flow. The coordinate system is defined so that x and y directions are taken along the stretching surface and the z-axis is perpendicular to the surface. It is assumed that the sheet stretches a Casson fluid with non-linear velocities and (where a and b are constants) implying that the surface stretching velocities act along the XY-plane.

The rheological equation of state for an isotropic and incompressible flow of a Casson fluid is as follows.

$$\tau_{ij} = 2(\mu_B + p_y / \sqrt{2\pi})e_{ij}, \quad \pi > \pi_c \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_{ij} = 2\mu_B + p_y / \sqrt{2\pi}e_{ij}, \quad \pi < \pi_c \quad (2)$$

Here, μ_B is the plastic dynamic viscosity of non-Newtonian fluid, $\pi = e_{ij}e_{ij}$ and e_{ij} are the $(i, j)^{th}$ component of the deformation rate, π is the product of the component of the deformation rate with itself, π_c is a critical value of π based on non-Newtonian model, p_y is the yield stress of the fluid.

The governing equations can be written as

Continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (1)$$

(1)

Momentum equation

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} = \mu \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} - \frac{\delta B_0^2}{\rho_{nf}} u - \frac{\vartheta_{nf}}{K^*} u \quad (2)$$

$$u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} = \mu \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial z^2} - \frac{\delta B_0^2}{\rho_{nf}} v - \frac{\vartheta_{nf}}{K^*} v \quad (3)$$

Energy equation

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} - \frac{1}{\rho c_p} \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial z} + \frac{(\rho c_p)_{np}}{\rho c_p} \times \left(D_B \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} + \frac{D_T}{T_\infty} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z}\right)^2 \right) + \frac{Q_0}{\rho c_p} (T - T_\infty) \quad (4)$$

(4)

Concentration equation

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} = D_m \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} + \frac{D_m K_T}{T_m} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \quad (5)$$

(5)

The corresponding boundary conditions are

$$u = U_w = a(x + y)^n, \quad v = V_w = b(x + y)^n, \quad w = 0, \quad T = T_w, \quad D_B \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} + \frac{D_T}{T_\infty} \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = 0 \quad \text{at } z = 0$$

$$u \rightarrow 0, \quad v \rightarrow 0, \quad T \rightarrow T_\infty, \quad C \rightarrow C_\infty \quad \text{as } z \rightarrow \infty$$

Where, u, v and w denote the velocity components of the fluid along the x-, y-, and z-axes, respectively. The kinematic viscosity of the fluid is denoted by ν . The

thermal diffusivity is given by $\alpha = \frac{k}{\rho C_p}$, where k is the thermal conductivity, ρ is the density of the Casson fluid. C_p is the specific heat constant pressure. The specific capacity of the nanoparticle is denoted by $C_p(\rho C_p)_{np}$. The coefficients β and λ correspond to the Brownian motion and thermophoretic diffusion respectively. The nanoparticle concentration is represented by C , while T and T_∞ denote the fluid temperature and the ambient (free-stream) temperature, respectively. The term $\frac{a}{(x+y)^{1-n}}$ represents the radiative heat flux. The applied magnetic field is expressed as $B_0 = \frac{a}{(x+y)^{1-n}}$, where a and n are constants related to the magnetic field intensity.

Solution procedure

We now apply the following similarity transformation

$$u = a(x+y)^n f'(\eta), \quad v = b(x+y)^n g'(\eta), \quad \eta = \sqrt{\frac{a}{\beta}}(x+y)^{(n-1)/2} z,$$

$$w = -\sqrt{a\beta}(x+y)^{(n-1)/2} \left[\frac{(n+1)}{2}(f) + \frac{(n+1)}{2}(g) + \frac{(n-1)}{2}\eta(f' + g') \right],$$

$$\theta(\eta) = \frac{T-T_\infty}{T_w-T_\infty}, \quad \phi(\eta) = \frac{C-C_\infty}{C_w-C_\infty},$$

$$T = \frac{T_w}{\alpha} \left(\frac{\beta}{a(n+1)(x+y)^{n-1}} \right)^{1/2} \theta(\eta) + T_\infty, \quad C = \frac{C_w}{\alpha} \left(\frac{\beta}{a(n+1)(x+y)^{n-1}} \right)^{1/2} \phi(\eta)$$

(7)

Upon applying the aforementioned transformations, the continuity equation is identically satisfied, and equations (2)-(5) are thereby reduced to the following forms,

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) f'''' + \left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right) (f + \lambda g) f'' - (n(f' + g') + M + K) f' = 0$$

(8)

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) g'''' + \left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right) (f + \lambda g) g'' - (n(f' + g') + M + K) g' = 0$$

(9)

$$\left(1 + \frac{4}{3}R\right) \theta'' + \left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right) Pr(f + \lambda g)\theta' + Pr(Nb\theta'\phi' + Nt\theta'^2 + Q\theta)$$

(10)

$$\phi'' + Sc\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right) (f + \lambda g)\phi' + Sc\frac{Nt}{Nb}\theta''$$

(11)

Given boundary conditions

$$f'(\eta) = 1, \quad g'(\eta) = 1, \quad f(\eta) = 0, \quad g(\eta) = 0, \quad \theta(\eta) = 1, \quad Nb\phi'(\eta) + Nt\theta'(\eta) = 0 \quad \text{at } \eta = 0$$

$$f'(\eta) = 0, \quad g'(\eta) = 0, \quad \theta(\eta) = 0, \quad \phi(\eta) = 0, \quad \text{at } \eta \rightarrow \infty$$

(12)

Where,

$$\beta = \mu_B \left(\frac{\sqrt{\pi c}}{P_y} \right), \quad \lambda = \frac{b}{a}, \quad M = \frac{\delta B_0^2}{a\rho f'}, \quad Pr = \frac{\beta}{\alpha}, \quad Sc = \frac{\beta}{D_B}, \quad Nb = \frac{(\rho_c)P D_B C_\infty}{(\rho^c) f \theta},$$

$$Nt = \frac{(\rho_c)P D_T C(T_w - T_\infty)}{(\rho^c) f \theta T_\infty}, \quad K = \frac{K^*}{a}$$

Skin friction coefficient, Nusselt number and Sherwood number

The skin friction coefficient along the x-axis and y-axis are denoted by C_{fx} and C_{fy}

which are defined as

$$C_{fx} = \frac{\tau_{wx}}{\rho_f U_w^2}, \quad C_{fy} = \frac{\tau_{wy}}{\rho_f U_w^2},$$

In the above expressions τ_{wx} and τ_{wy} are the wall shear stress along x-axis and y-axis respectively.

$$\sqrt{Re_x} C_{fx} = f''(0), \quad \sqrt{Re_x} C_{fy} = g''(0),$$

Where $Re_x = \frac{U_w(x)x}{\nu}$ is the local Reynolds number

The local Nusselt number and Sherwood number are expressed by following expressions

$$\frac{Nu_x}{\sqrt{Re_x}} = -(1 + R)\theta'(0), \quad \frac{Sh_x}{\sqrt{Re_x}} = -\phi'(0)$$

Result and Discussion

The coupled non-linear ordinary differential equations (8-11) with given boundary conditions (12) were numerically solved using MATLAB bvp4c solver, and the obtained results are illustrated graphically in the figures. The obtained results illustrate the influence of various non-dimensional parameters, namely Casson parameter β , stretching ratio λ , Magnetic parameter M , Porosity parameter K , Radiation parameter R , Prandtl number Pr , thermophoresis parameter Nt , Brownian motion parameter Nb , heat generation parameter Q , Schmidt number Sc on velocity profiles $f'(\eta)$ and $g'(\eta)$, temperature profiles $\theta(\eta)$, concentration profiles $\phi(\eta)$. Taking $\beta = 0.2, \lambda = 1.2, M = 0.5, K = 0.1, R = 0.5, Pr = 2, Nt = 0.2, Nb = 0.7, Q = 0.1, Sc = 15$.

Fig. (1-2) show the impact of Casson parameter on velocity profiles, temperature profiles and concentration profiles. It is observed that an increase in the Casson parameter leads to a reduction in velocity profiles and an enhancement in temperature profiles and concentration profiles. This behavior arises because, as the Casson parameter increases, the fluid tends to behave more like a Newtonian fluid. The higher plasticity associated with the Casson fluid contributes to greater heat generation, resulting in increased temperature and reduced velocity.

Fig. 1 effect of Casson parameter β on velocity profiles $f'(\eta)$ and $g'(\eta)$

Fig. 2 effect of Casson parameter β on temperature and concentration profiles $\theta(\eta)$ and $\phi(\eta)$

Fig. (3-4) the influence of Power rule index on velocity profiles, temperature profiles and concentration profiles. An increasing value of n reduced the velocity

profiles, temperature profiles and concentration profiles.

Fig. 3 effect of Power rule index n on velocity profiles $f'(\eta)$ and $g'(\eta)$

Fig. 4 effect of Power rule index n on temperature and concentration profiles $\theta(\eta)$ and $\phi(\eta)$

Fig. (5) shows the effect of stretching ratio parameter on velocity profiles. An enhancement in the stretching ratio parameter leads to a suppression of the fluid velocity within the boundary layer.

Fig. 5 effect of stretching ratio λ on velocity profiles $f'(\eta)$ and $g'(\eta)$

Fig. (6) the impact of magnetic parameter is observed on the distribution of velocity profiles. The application of a stronger magnetic field i.e. larger magnetic parameter induced a Lorentz force that resists fluid motion, leading to a decrease in the velocity profiles.

Fig. 6 effect of Magnetic parameter M on velocity profiles $f'(\eta)$ and $g'(\eta)$

Fig. (7) illustrates the porosity parameter on velocity profiles. As the porosity parameter K becomes larger, the fluid motion in both directions diminishes due to the intensified resistance imposed by the porous structure according to Darcy's law.

Fig. 7 effect of Porosity parameter K on velocity profiles $f'(\eta)$ and $g'(\eta)$

Fig. (8) this figure indicated that the effect of radiation parameter on temperature and concentration profiles. The temperature profile is elevated, and the concentration profile is reduced when the radiation parameter increases.

Fig. 8 effect of Radiation parameter on temperature and concentration profiles $\theta(\eta)$ and $\phi(\eta)$

Fig. (9) shows the effect of Prandtl number on temperature and concentration profiles. With rising Prandtl number values, the temperature within the boundary layer decreases, owing to the feeble thermal diffusivity associated with higher-Prandtl-number fluids.

Fig. 9 effect of Prandtl number on temperature and concentration profiles $\theta(\eta)$ and $\phi(\eta)$

Fig. (10) effect of thermophoresis and Brownian motion parameter on concentration profiles. It is observed that increasing the thermophoresis parameter results in a noticeable decline in the concentration profile. Lower thermophoresis forces yield smaller concentration gradient and more uniform nanoparticle distribution. Enhancing the Brownian motion parameter produces an increase in the concentration distribution. Physically, the Brownian force acts to drive particles against the concentration gradient, promoting a more uniform distribution in the nanofluid.

Fig. 10 effect of thermophoresis and Brownian motion parameter on concentration profiles $\phi(\eta)$

Fig. (11) shows the influence of the Schmidt number on concentration profiles. A higher Schmidt number leads to a broader concentration distribution. At elevated Sc values the particles are relatively large and exhibit increased diffusivity, making this mode of deposition increasingly significant.

Fig. 11 effect of heat source parameter on temperature and concentration profiles $\theta(\eta)$ and $\phi(\eta)$

Table 1 the variation of $-f''(0)$, $-g''(0)$, $-\theta'(0)$, and $-\phi'(0)$ with respect to β, K, n and λ parameters are given in table. The skin friction coefficient increases as the Casson fluid parameter, porosity parameter, power rule index and stretching ratio parameter become larger. The local Nusselt number decrease and Sherwood numbers increases for power rule index and stretching ratio parameter. For Casson fluid parameter local Nusselt number increases and Sherwood number

reduced. For porosity parameter local Nusselt number and Sherwood number decreases.

Table 1 computational value of skin friction coefficient, Nusselt number and Sherwood number for different parameters ($\beta = 0.2, n = 1, Nt = 0.2, Nb = 0.5, Sc = 1, \lambda = 1, R = 0.5, Q = 0.1, Pr = 8.0, M = 0.2, K = 0.1$).

β	K	n	λ	$-f''(0)$	$-g''(0)$	$-\theta'(0)$	$-\phi'(0)$
0.2	0.1	1	1	0.6192	0.6192	-2.1788	0.8715
0.3				0.7285	0.7285	-2.1530	0.8612
0.4				0.8106	0.8106	-2.1336	0.8534
	0.2			0.6325	0.6325	-2.1757	0.8702
	0.3			0.6465	0.6465	-2.1726	0.8690
		2		0.8103	0.8103	-2.6987	1.0794
		3		0.9644	0.9644	-3.1339	1.2535
			1.2	0.6289	0.6289	-2.2990	0.9196
			1.4	0.6386	0.6386	-2.4133	0.9653

Conclusion

The three-dimensional magnetohydrodynamic Casson nanofluid flow past a non-linearly stretching surface in presence of porous media is examined. The following are the observations obtained as a result of the investigation into current research paper.

1. Velocity profiles in both x and y directions are reduced for increasing value of Casson parameter, power rule index and stretching ratio parameter.
2. Temperature profiles enhanced for Casson parameter, radiation parameter and heat source parameter.
3. Concentration profiles increased for larger value of thermophoresis parameter and Schmidt number.
4. Concentration profiles decreased for larger value of Brownian motion parameter and heat source parameter.

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